

COGNITIVE POETICS IN THE ANALYSIS OF THE NATURALIST NARRATIVE IN THEODORE DREISER'S SISTER CARRIE

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Abstract

This article investigates Theodore Dreiser's novel *Sister Carrie* through the framework of cognitive poetics. It analyses how cognitive mechanisms such as figure-ground organization, schema activation, deixis, conceptual metaphor and text-world theory influence readers' perception of the narrative and reveal the naturalist representation of capitalist society and the illusion of the American Dream.

Keywords: cognitive poetics, Theodore Dreiser, *Sister Carrie*, naturalism, American Dream, narrative cognition

Theodore Dreiser is the representative of naturalism in American literature of the late 19th and early 20th century. The period is marked by the processes of industrialization and urbanization of the metropolises such as Chicago, New York and Philadelphia. The age of rapid development required the same pace of documentation of events which led to the emergence of this writing style depicting every detail of changes. Mechanization and importance of materialism forced authors explore the inner world of the member of capitalist society: moral ambiguity, core ambitions and fears, and the effects of transformation on their life.

Theodore Dreiser's journalistic experience made him to apply the techniques of "putter-inner" style in his fiction illustrating peculiarities of American society in the period of industrialization.¹ His early publications such as "Free", "Lost Phoebe" and "Nigger Jeff" are the reflection of the accumulated knowledge and observation. The true realization of Dreiser's naturalist method and illustration of his deterministic worldview appeared in his first novel "Sister Carrie".

Initially, the publication of *Sister Carrie* faced up with a number of challenges from promoters. The sincerity with which Dreiser presents the affair of a young woman with two men from the upper class made the book, in Frank Doubleday's view, impossible to promote for any respectable publishing house.

The illustration of the class distinction was the need of the historical period as the one of the tools to research the most doubtful questions of uncertainty in the period of rapid transformation. June Howard explores that the "pessimistic determinism" of Theodore Dreiser in regard of the unpredictability of environmental forces influences not only on the lives of those without social incentives but the privileged ones as well.²

In addition to the historical and sociological analysis of *Sister Carrie* by Theodore Dreiser, cognitive poetics examines how readers mentally process and build up narrative meaning. As

¹ Thomas Wolfe, "A letter from Thomas Wolfe" in F.Scott Fitzgerald, *The Crack-Up*, edited by Edmund Wilson (New York: New Directions, 1945), p. 314

² June Howard, "Form and History in American Literary Naturalism", Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 1985, p.50

highlighted by Stockwell, Gavins and Steen, this study analyses with the use of general cognitive mechanisms such as figure-ground organization, deixis, schema activation, and text-world building. The perception of the reader is governed by these mechanisms and cognitive-poetic principles allows to comprehend not only the philosophical context of naturalist fiction, but also reveal its textual and cognitive one through narrative building.

The attention of the reader cannot be focused on different topics equally. There is always the front plan that is featured with transformation and movement and the background being passive and uncontrollable. The front plan is called the figure and the background is the ground. Language pushes particular elements forward and others into the background.

The specific attention is paid to the character's name and the relation to its temper. Reflecting all techniques of bibliographic narrative Dreiser introduces Carrie in the beginning of her development in a big city. Initially, Chicago is the ground according to the cognitive poetics theory. The whole city is constructed to emphasize the distinction between classes, and reader, therefore, understands that their ambitions are detached to this illusion of a better life in a great city that provides equal opportunities for all members of society – an American Dream.

The function of this transition of roles between figure and ground is to show the power of the system that controlled the fates of characters in regards of money, material possession and surrounding. The moment of disillusionment with an American dream comes with this shift, when the reader realizes that the character no longer controls his or her choices and desires.

The concept of prototype is explained as the established familiar patterns in human mind connected with daily experiences. Dreiser illustrate the character development of Carrie Meeber in expectance of moral fall and disillusionment

The urbanisation processes are presented to be beyond the control of the characters which gradually turns Chicago into the figure and Carrie into the ground as naturalism explores the influence of environmental circumstances such as economy, origin and behavior on the life of people. For Carrie the metropolis is still uncontrollable, but no longer passive.

Dreiser uses symbolism to ensure the reader of the inevitability of character's degradation. The description of coal mine is usually associated with black color, and this color, in its turn, with negative experience in life. Minnie's mind illustrated the potential outcome of her sister's choice, relating the lure of money to ultimate fall, which is the social prototype of the right choices.

The reader expects the redemption arc following the way that Carrie opts. However, she achieves everything she has ever wished for, the wonders of financially sustainable life, fashionable clothing and favourite job.

Socially accepted "*wrong*" decisions in the moral ambiguity made her successful and famous among the same people who set those prototypes. There is no punishment for immoral choices as the reader may expect: rather the emotional emptiness and soul loneliness become the main consequence of such an inner drive.

By foregrounding technique, Dreiser emphasizes the importance of spiritual and emotional wellness over the material world. From naturalist perspective, material challenges in his fiction are solvable while the state of inner world cannot be controlled by the external circumstances.

Deixis in cognitive poetics is the shift in the mind into the character's position in time, space and perception, which is traditionally called deictic shift. In literature deixis shows us from whose position we are experiencing the events.

Theodore Dreiser uses deixis in *Sister Carrie* primarily to illustrate the effect of industrialism and urbanisation on the life of ordinary girl from suburban area. Firstly, he describes Chicago not according to the historical knowledge or facts, but through Carrie Meeber's vision. The usage of words such as "there" and "she looked" gives the reader not only the immediate picture of the city, but the experience of its size, unpredictability and positive expectations of better life. the spatial "here" of the reader is directly connected to Carrie's "here" – the reader perceive the city through the protagonist's attention.

Another technique is applied to depict the internal world of the character. In chapter VII, which is named as "*The Lure of the Material*", in order to show how the world of materialism operates, Dreiser starts from generalised statement.

This shift from general to individual calls deictic shift and applied to emphasize the certain idea. The detailed counting and description of the objects Carrie pays attention to is important to share the reader the protagonist's character-bound view and reveal her true desires.

The way in which the actions of the characters are conceptualised in the fiction is called cognitive grammar. The concept answers the following reader's questions: "Who is active?", "Who initiates actions?" and "Who is affected?".

Theodore Dreiser often uses passive construction for a better depiction of deterministic ideology in naturalism. Independence and authority of agency is weak in his fiction and characters rather experience the influence of abstract agents than making life decisions on their own.

The appliance of passive voice in narration ensures the reader that characters no longer control their lives.

Schema in cognitive poetics is the certain patterns of knowledge that readers store in mind. Script, on the other hand, is the expected sequence of actions related to specific area or institution in life. Cognitive schema and script are interconnected in literature.

Theodore Dreiser uses schema and script in *Sister Carrie* to question the true values of life. Romantic affairs turn to abandon the means of protection and success but rather leads to emotional tension. Carrie starts her relationship with Drouet because of the power and money that he has as she feels that financial stability can protect her. Female vulnerability is in the search of male agency following the naturalist approach of the author. The script of expected stability is activated in the reader's mind. However, the protection that Drouet gave her didn't provide the emotional security as Carrie became abandoned and subtly suffer from loneliness.

This is the schema disruption applied by Dreiser to draw the attention of the reader to the idea that material wellness is not equal to the mental one. Careless character of Drouet was not able to provide the emotional fulfillment for Carrie.

Dreiser expresses the disillusionment with American dream and explains how the capitalist world operates in reality through the use of this schema. Industrialized cities shaped her initial desire of material possessions and left her without sense of true fulfillment.

The concept of discourse world in cognitive poetics reflect the shared reality between the author, the reader and the cultural context in which the text is written and interpreted. The

discourse world shares the historical, social and ideological knowledge in the background and does not refer only to narrated events.

The discourse world in *Sister Carrie* is built up around the context of capitalist America in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

The novel explores urbanization of cities such as Chicago and New York, the capitalist system and the idea of gender inequality. Despite the fact, that these elements are not discussed by Dreiser directly, they are still visible in the background or as a reflection of character's actions and decisions.

The reader can feel Carrie's desire for material comfort, the influence of male protection and the ambition for success in this discourse world. This is also the mention of the American dream in forming expectations and judgements.

Referring to discourse world allows Dreiser to abandon moral judgement in regards of determinism. He does not comment on the actions of characters, while illustrating the conditions of the way to success in capitalist society as an objective description. So the responsibility for interpreting and comprehending the motivation of the characters depends on the reader.

Conceptual metaphor theory is applied to make the reader experience abstract concepts through specific physical experiences. Traditional metaphors such as "*Life is a journey*", "*desire is hunger*" and "*success is up*" also function in literary text.

Cognitive poetics defines the concept of literature as parable in shaping a model for understanding social or psychological processes. A parable operates here as reflection of specific fiction in an extended pattern in human mind.

Theodore Dreiser uses biographic approach in writing *Sister Carrie* but does not refer to the fiction as a personal story of Carrie Meeber. It is the general reflection of an inner drive for material success and recognition in a capitalist society. Her development, relationships and emotional emptiness are not personal patterns, but rather the model for the whole society. Through this parable the idea of the formation of desire by material world and social expectations is described for deeper understanding of the system of the period.

It allows to avoid the moral commentary in the reader's mind and rather completely grasp the capitalist world and its conditions, while making its society the main product. It avoids fixed interpretation to open up the scope for broader analysis of inner world of the characters.

The theory of text world in cognitive poetics explores the mental world constructed by the reader by consuming a literary text. There are several worlds that shape in different level: the text world is the fictional reality and sub-worlds appear in character's thoughts, imagination and dreams.

The text world and sub-worlds are vividly divided in *Sister Carrie* through the true realm of the metropolises and the imaginary world that Carrie wishes for. She imagines success in enjoyment and comforts reflected through material world, romantic protection and social recognition.

The sub-world traditionally faces with the reality of text world. Industrial cities are ready to provide her the material fulfillment, while leaving Carrie to fight with emotional loneliness in her internal world. The strong distinction between expectations and external conditions creates the endless need for unachievable state.

This pressure between text world and sub-worlds does not allow to intertwine them in the reader's mind.

In conclusion, cognitive poetics provides an effective approach to understand *Sister Carrie* as a naturalist novel that operates through cognitive tools and elements shaping reader's perception. Theodore Dreiser's text does not guide the reader what to think, but constructs conditions that influence the emergence of meaning in mind. Through analysing these cognitive processes, the novel represents modern life as emotionally unfulfilled in the achievement of material success, and how human inner world remains dissatisfied within the structures of capitalist society.

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